

Experiences in Analytics

Start of Block: Objectives and Conditions

Q1 Development Experiences in Data Analytics

We are exploring the processes by which data analysts learn and work. The information in this survey will help us diagnose and suggest changes in practice that could help both amateur and professional analytics programming communities.

Q2

Before proceeding, please look at the following terms to ensure that you consent to participation:

General terms of research participation:

You are being asked to take part in a research study. Your participation in this study is voluntary. You have the right to be a part of this study, to choose not to participate, or to stop participating at any time without penalty.

The purpose of research studies is to gain a better understanding of a certain topic or issue. You are not guaranteed any personal benefits from being in a study. Research studies also may pose risks to those that participate.

In this consent form, you will find specific details about the research in which you are being asked to participate. If you do not understand something in this form it is your right to ask the researcher for clarification or more information. [A copy of this consent form will be provided to you \(linked here and below\)](#). If at any time you have questions about your participation, do not hesitate to contact the researcher(s) named below.

Details of this research:

We are gathering the experiences of data analysts to understand how they work and what they use to work. This knowledge will help us characterize how a community of data analysts differs from professional software engineers, allowing us to better diagnose the changes in practice that could be made to benefit more communities of people who program in any capacity.

If you agree to participate in this study, you will be asked to recount your history and experience with data analytics in baseball as it concerns software engineering practices. Survey and

interview topics will focus on documentation, learning materials, and steps in the overall process of designing software, large or small, suited to your specific needs.

There are minimal risks associated with this study. You will not receive any compensation for participating. Your participation is helping the software engineering and data analytics communities, by giving us insight into new or more effective ways to support programming needs.

The information in the study records will be kept confidential to the full extent allowed by law. Data will be stored securely in accordance with industry best practices, and will be anonymized after collection. No reference will be made in oral or written reports which could link you to the study. You will NOT be asked to write your name on any study materials so that no one can match your identity to the answers that you provide. This study is partly supported by the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD), and so representatives of the DoD are authorized to view research materials and results.

Contact details:

If you have questions at any time about the study or the procedures, you may contact the researcher, Justin A. Middleton, at jamiddl2@ncsu.edu. If you feel you have not been treated according to the descriptions in this form, or your rights as a participant in research have been violated during the course of this project, you may contact the IRB office at irb-coordinator@ncsu.edu or by phone at 1-919- 515-8754.

Meaning of consent:

By selecting "Yes, I consent to the above conditions," you are stating the following:

"I have read and understand the above information. [I have received a copy of this form](#). I agree to participate in this study with the understanding that I may choose not to participate or to stop participating at any time without penalty or loss of benefits to which I am otherwise entitled.

Q3

Do you agree to the above conditions?

- Yes, I consent to the above conditions (1)
- No, I do not consent (2)

End of Block: Objectives and Conditions

Start of Block: Professional Backgrounds

Q4 For this survey, we can use the following definition of data analytics:

"Data analytics is the multidisciplinary science of quantitatively and qualitatively examining data for the purpose of drawing new conclusions or insights (exploratory or predictive), or for extracting and proving (confirmatory or fact-based) hypotheses about that information for decision-making and action."

from L. Cao, "Data Science: A Comprehensive Overview", 2017

Q5 Have you ever practiced data analytics to any extent?

- Yes, professionally (1)
 - Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education (3)
 - No (2)
-

Display This Question:

If Have you ever practiced data analytics to any extent? = Yes, professionally

Or Have you ever practiced data analytics to any extent? = Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education

Q6 How many years of experience do you have in data analytics?
Your best estimate is sufficient.

- Less than 1 year (1)
 - Between 1 and 2 years (2)
 - Between 2 and 5 years (3)
 - Between 5 and 10 years (4)
 - Between 10 and 20 years (5)
 - More than 20 years (6)
-

Q7 Have you ever practiced **baseball** analytics to any extent?
That is, analytics on baseball data.

- Yes, professionally (1)
 - Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education (5)
 - No (3)
-

Display This Question:

*If Have you ever practiced baseball analytics to any extent? That is, analytics on baseball data. =
Yes, professionally*

*Or Have you ever practiced baseball analytics to any extent? That is, analytics on baseball data. =
Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education*

Q8 How many years of experience do you have in baseball analytics?

- Less than 1 year (1)
 - Between 1 and 2 years (2)
 - Between 2 and 5 years (3)
 - Between 5 and 10 years (4)
 - Between 10 and 20 years (5)
 - More than 20 years (6)
-

Q9 Do you practice any form of programming or software engineering?

We include a wide range of practice, from building complex software systems to writing database queries in SQL or spreadsheet formulae.

- Yes, professionally (1)
 - Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education (3)
 - No (2)
-

Display This Question:

If Do you practice any form of programming or software engineering? We include a wide range of pract... = Yes, professionally

Or Do you practice any form of programming or software engineering? We include a wide range of pract... = Yes, strictly as a hobby or in education

Q10 How many years of experience do you have in programming?

- Less than 1 year (1)
- Between 1 and 2 years (2)
- Between 2 and 5 years (3)
- Between 5 and 10 years (4)
- Between 10 and 20 years (5)
- More than 20 years (6)

End of Block: Professional Backgrounds

Start of Block: Professional Experiences p2

Display This Question:

If Have you ever practiced data analytics to any extent? = No

And Have you ever practiced baseball analytics to any extent? That is, analytics on baseball data. = No

Q11 Thank you for your interest, but since you have recorded no experience in data analytics and that is our primary interest, we will not take any more of your time.

Skip To: End of Survey If Thank you for your interest, but since you have recorded no experience in data analytics and that... Is Displayed

End of Block: Professional Experiences p2

Start of Block: Professional Experiences p2

Q12 If you currently practice a professional occupation, how do you describe your position title?

- Title: (1) _____
 - Not applicable for me. (2)
-

Q13 On which continent is your professional work based?

- Africa (1)
 - Asia or Middle East (2)
 - Australia or Oceania (3)
 - Europe (4)
 - North or Central America (5)
 - South America (6)
-

Q14 What is the highest level of formal education you have experienced?

- Less than high school (1)
 - High school graduate (2)
 - Some college (3)
 - 2 year degree (4)
 - 4 year degree (5)
 - Professional degree (6)
 - Master's (7)
 - Doctorate (8)
-

Q15 If you have graduated from some form of higher education, what are the subjects of your primary degrees?

- Mathematics (1)
 - Statistics (2)
 - Business (3)
 - Economics (4)
 - Other Social Science (5)
-

- Information Technology (IT) (6)
 - Computer Science/Software Engineering (7)
 - Other Engineering (8)
-

Others (if multiple, separate by commas): (9)

N/A (10)

Q16 Are there any subjects relevant to data analytics that you have taught yourself?
"Teaching yourself" includes reading textbooks or self-directed online resources, beyond what has been included in your compulsory education.

- Mathematics (1)
 - Statistics (2)
 - Business (3)
 - Economics (4)
 - Other Social Science (5)
-

- Information Technology (IT) (6)
 - Computer Science/Software Engineering (7)
 - Other Engineering (8)
-

Others (if multiple, separate by commas): (9)

None (10)

End of Block: Professional Experiences p2

Start of Block: Suggested Framework

Display This Question:

*If Have you ever practiced baseball analytics to any extent? That is, analytics on baseball data. = No
And Have you ever practiced data analytics to any extent? = Yes, professionally*

Q17 Please answer the questions on this survey in terms of your most recent experiences with professional data analytics.

Display This Question:

If Have you ever practiced baseball analytics to any extent? That is, analytics on baseball data. != No

Q18 Please answer the questions on this page and following pages in terms of your experiences with **baseball analytics**, even if you have practiced other types of analytics.

Q19

If you marked that you do not program or script, you can nevertheless answer in terms of learning the software products you use for analyses.

By "documentation" or "docs," we mean any documents or resources intended to inform or teach a software user how to use the software, including product manuals, tutorials, and online classes.

By "tools," we mean, in general, any software product that supports you in writing a script or program, including the ready-made software libraries for that language and the environment in which you write your code.

End of Block: Suggested Framework

Start of Block: Learning Resources

Q20 Please rate the following resources on how important they were to prepare you for the analytics work you've done in the last year.

	Not at all important (1)	Slightly important (2)	Moderately important (3)	Very important (4)	Extremely important (5)
Formal education (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Practice through professional responsibilities (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Practice through personal projects (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reading blogs and social media (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reading academic resources (e.g. textbooks, journals) (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reading official tool documentation (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reading or participating in online educational resources (e.g. tutorials or MOOCs) (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reading or participating in Q&A websites (e.g. StackOverflow) (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Organized analytics or programming competitions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(e.g. Kaggle,
Hackathons)
(9)

Observing or
conversing
with
experienced
mentors and
peers (10)

Q21 Do you have any other learning resources, and if so, what would you rate them?

End of Block: Learning Resources

Start of Block: Learning Resources p2

Q22 How does the inclusion of the following types of *content* in documentation affect your choice to use the tool or docs?

"Preference for" means you want it included, "preference against" means you'd rather not see it.

	Strong Preference For (29)	Preference For (30)	No Preference (31)	Preference Against (32)	Strong Preference Against (33)
Author credentials (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Discussion of design choices in making the tool (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Code examples (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sample scenarios for which a feature should be used (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Runtime or memory efficiency of tool features (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Support communities (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Common errors and their fixes (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
How to contribute to the tool's development (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ratings or reviews from other people (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Explicitly
identified best
practices (10)

Discrete,
step-by-step
instructions
(11)

Copy-and-
pastable
code recipes
(12)

Q23 Is there any other supplementary content that you think documentation should have that isn't included above?

Q24 What do you see as the biggest failures in most documentation?

Many of the below can be considered problems, but select only those which you feel you often encounter in your practice.

- I see no consistent failures (1)
- Difficult to find online (2)
- Accessibility problems for people with disability (3)
- Not open-source (4)
- Too much information / wordiness (5)
- Inability to search for keywords (6)
- Not enough pictures or mixed media (7)
- Not enough included code (8)
- Paywalls (9)
- Not enough community support (10)
- Expects prior experience (11)
- Out of date (12)
- Incomplete feature descriptions (13)
- Inconsistent feature descriptions (14)
- Other: (15) _____

End of Block: Learning Resources p2

Start of Block: Process Questions

Q25 Each of your projects is probably slightly different, but think of the "typical project" as a hypothetical project that involves the techniques that you use frequently (e.g. more than half the time) in your actual projects.

(Optional) In regular language, describe what a "typical" project looks like for you. For example, what is its goal, and what data does it use? What did your final products look like?

You can answer this either with the hypothetical totally average project, or with a real example of a project you worked on.

Q26 On a typical project, do you work with other people in data analytics?

- Yes, a project manager or boss (1)
 - Yes, other researchers or analysts (2)
 - Yes, a client outside your organization (3)
 - Yes, friends or acquaintances outside of professional work (4)
 - Yes, someone else (5)
-
- No, I work independently (6)

Display This Question:

If On a typical project, do you work with other people in data analytics? != No, I work independently

Q27 With how many people do you coordinate directly on a typical project?

Display This Question:

If On a typical project, do you work with other people in data analytics? != No, I work independently

Q28 How much of your data analytic experience is described by the following management structure (must total 100%)?

I receive rigid guidelines or requirements from a manager or client. : _____ (1)

I receive guidelines from a manager or client but retain some flexibility about how I accomplish it. : _____ (2)

I balance guidance from a manager or client and my own interests and goal. : _____ (3)

I set my own goals but receive input from a boss, client, or peers. : _____ (4)

I receive no external input. : _____ (5)

Total : _____

Display This Question:

If On a typical project, do you work with other people in data analytics? != No, I work independently

Q29 If you receive guidelines from someone else, what do they dictate (more than half of the time)?

Not selecting an option means you choose that detail for yourself.

- Which question to answer (1)
 - Which data to use (2)
 - Which analytical methodology or techniques to use (3)
 - Which software or programming tools to use (4)
 - How efficient any software must be (5)
 - When to have it done (6)
 - Which format or medium to report results in (7)
 - Whom you can talk to about it and how much you can share (8)
 - Something else: (9) _____
 - I choose all of the above for myself (10)
-

Q30 How well do the following statements about a project process describe your experience?

	Always (1)	Most of the time (2)	About half the time (3)	Sometimes (4)	Never (5)
I (or my team) scrape or create my own data. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I downloaded data that someone else scraped or created. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have (or set) a deadline for project completion. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have data before I know what question to ask. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I decide an analytical method I want to use before I have my question. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Q31 Before you begin programming, do you spend any time making designs for your analytics scripts or methods?

- Yes, I write pseudocode or code-like comments. (1)
 - Yes, I draw diagrams. (2)
 - Yes, I describe it in textual documents. (3)
 - Yes, I describe it conversation with someone else, written or verbal. (4)
 - Yes, I scribble informal notes. (5)
 - Yes, I create some other notation: (7)
-
- Yes, but it's exclusively thought. (6)
 - No, I begin coding as soon as possible. (8)

Display This Question:

If Before you begin programming, do you spend any time making designs for your analytics scripts or... != No, I begin coding as soon as possible.

Q32 Do you consult your design while working on your project?

- Always: I perform all of my work while simultaneously consulting and updating the design documents. (1)
- Often; I verify most changes I make with my design documents as I make them. (2)
- Rarely; I consult the documents every few days, weeks, or milestones otherwise to measure progress. (3)
- No (4)

Display This Question:

If Before you begin programming, do you spend any time making designs for your analytics scripts or... != No, I begin coding as soon as possible.

Q33 Does anyone else look at your design documents?

- Yes, a project manager (1)
 - Yes, other researchers or analysts (2)
 - Yes, a client outside your organization (3)
 - Yes, friends or acquaintances outside of professional work (4)
 - Yes, someone else: (5)
-
- No (6)

Q34 In what proportion of your projects are you expected to deliver or share the following with your audience or client?

	All (1)	More than half (2)	About half (3)	Less than half (4)	None (5)
The summary of my findings. (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
The analytical methodology or techniques I used. (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
The scripts or programs I wrote. (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
The data I used. (4)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q35 Is there anything else you are expected to deliver with results?

Page Break

Q36 Which of the following tools do you frequently use for your work?

- R (1)
 - Python (2)
 - IBM SPSS Tools (3)
 - SAS (4)
 - Microsoft Excel (5)
 - Stata (6)
 - JavaScript (7)
 - SQL (8)
 - Java (9)
 - Ruby (10)
 - Tableau (11)
 - MATLAB (12)
 - Weka (13)
 - KNIME (14)
 - Other (if multiple missing, choose most important in your workflow): (15)
-

Q37 In what ways do you test the validity of your results (more than half the time)?

- Look at the results to see if they make intuitive sense. (1)
- Consult with other people to see if they think it makes intuitive sense. (2)
- Personally validate the underlying mathematics. (3)
- Informally test any programs I write (e.g. print statements). (4)
- Formally test any programs I write (e.g. test suites). (5)
- Benchmark my programs or validate estimators on already-understood data. (6)
- Split my data into testing and training sets and cross-validate. (7)
- Run any programs I write in different computing environments. (8)
- Something else: (9) _____
- I do not test or validate between analysis and completion. (10)

Q38 Do you have any other validation techniques not mentioned above?

Q39 In what ways do you back up versions of your work on a computer (more than half the time)?

- I save multiple versions on my computer with different filenames. (1)
- I print out and save physical copies of my work. (2)
- I save them to multiple computers or external harddrives. (3)
- I upload them to an online file system (e.g. Google Drive). (4)
- I use a versioning system on my personal computer (e.g. git). (5)
- I use a versioning system with a remote server (e.g. GitHub, BitBucket). (6)
- I do not use versions, I maintain only one ongoing file. (7)

Page Break

Q40 Do you consciously apply any of the following data mining/analytics processes to your work?

- CRISP-DM (1)
 - SEMMA (2)
 - KDD (3)
 - Something else: (4) _____
 - I have no consistent work process. (5)
-

Q41 How many times per typical project do you carry out phases as described below?

	I do this continually throughout the entire process (1)	Multiple discrete times (2)	Once (3)	None (4)	I don't do this/distinguish this from another phase (5)
Planning the project schedule (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Researching the problem domain (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Researching the resources available (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Formulating a question or hypothesis (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collecting data sources (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cleaning data (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Identifying relevant data (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reshaping data for analysis (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Designing the analytic approach (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Choosing an algorithm (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Building or coding the model (11)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tweaking or debugging the model (12)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Evaluating the results (13)	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpreting results (14)	<input type="radio"/>				
Reporting results (15)	<input type="radio"/>				
Automating the analysis for replication (16)	<input type="radio"/>				
Responding to feedback (17)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q42 Which phases take the most time?

- Planning the project schedule (1)
- Researching the problem domain (2)
- Researching the resources available (3)
- Formulating a question or hypothesis (4)
- Collecting data sources (5)
- Cleaning data (6)
- Identifying relevant data (7)
- Reshaping data for analysis (8)
- Designing the analytic approach (9)
- Choosing an algorithm (10)
- Building or coding the model (11)
- Tweaking or debugging the model (12)
- Evaluating the results (13)
- Interpreting results (14)
- Reporting results (15)
- Automating the analysis for replication (16)
- Responding to feedback (17)

Something not included above: (18)

Q43 Which phases cause the most frustration or are the most unpleasant?

- Planning the project schedule (1)
- Researching the problem domain (2)
- Researching the resources available (3)
- Formulating a question or hypothesis (4)
- Collecting data sources (5)
- Cleaning data (6)
- Identifying relevant data (7)
- Reshaping data for analysis (8)
- Designing the analytic approach (9)
- Choosing an algorithm (10)
- Building or coding the model (11)
- Tweaking or debugging the model (12)
- Evaluating the results (13)
- Interpreting results (14)
- Reporting results (15)
- Automating the analysis for replication (16)
- Responding to feedback (17)

Something not included above: (18)

Page Break

Q44 Which of these barriers, if mitigated, would save you the most frustration? Choose up to 3.

- Not enough material resources (e.g. money, equipment). (1)
- Not enough time. (2)
- Overcoming your own lack of experience. (3)
- Working with less experienced people. (4)
- Coordinating people to work together. (5)
- Finding and scraping sources for complex data. (6)
- Detecting and dealing with erroneous data. (7)
- Understanding complex data. (8)
- Remembering everything you need to know. (9)
- Unreliable software. (10)
- Unreliable software instructions or documentation. (11)
- Coordinating different softwares or libraries to work together. (12)
- Uncertainty of the legality of what you're working with. (13)
- Writing documentation for your methodology or software. (14)
- Explaining your results to your audience. (15)
- Lack of confidence in your results. (16)
- Lack of a supportive community. (17)
- Other (18) _____

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